

On standardrization of Addresses

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Abstract: On progressing world, where pigeons are no longer used to carry messages like as in fairy tales, and historical tales, need of standarization of address was felt, for physical and internet means. In this paper, author has attempted to describe address in standard form, allowing to be cited, as per available databases, uniqueness, and accuracy.

Keywords: Address, Citation of Address, Standarization of address, Arjun Dahal, arjundahalard

Introduction:

Our address of physical reality are more inclined towards permanent residentialship, where as our internet address too is being inclined towards uniqueness and on permanent basis. Here we present an example of address in citable form, without sinking in depth, to waste time, which not only author but as per author's guess, lot of peoples would feel lazy to study.

Citing Address:

An example of format of address is shown below:

Permanent: Name of Nation, State/Province, District, Postal Code/Zip Code, Municipality, Road, Street Address, House Number, P.O.Box Number

Temporary: Name of Nation, State/Province, District, Postal Code/Zip Code, Municipality, Road, Street Address, House Number

An example considered by author for his own address would be:

Permanent: Nepal, Province 1, Jhapa, 57216, Gauradaha, Daabi Birodh, ShreeSwoostaani, 1, 1

Temporary Address too would be similiar, for Domestic Purpose, or even for International Purpose.

Numerical Citation of Address:

As each nation has country codes, and numerical based values, all of them can be used in numerical based values, for more standardness. If we rely on assigning numbers to each values, on basis principle of counting, then still, same format can be used.

For an example, If we consider Nepal's country code, then all the values in citation as 1, then address would be:

Permanent: 1,1,1,57216,1,1,1,1,1.

Immediate question that would arise is, what does these numbers means, and to answer, we need to prepare database, as per counting, where each values begins from 1 till needed, depending upon individual population and their residence.

Author has used Postal code number of his village(Municipality), which is 57216, as address system isn't introduced properly in Nepal yet.Geographical co-ordinates too can be included, as per conviniency in the format of address.

Is the address in citable form?

The address we talked, are found in most of nations, where nomenclature can be found, but author lacks knowledge, if counting and assigning values has been done or not, to make a database, on basis of which, address can be made as citable, even with variation in address formats.

In Nepal, Kitta Number, Seat number too are used, which would provide description of land, if has any building constructed or not, due to factor of house number. Land with house number would mean, non-vacantness of land, and land without house number would mean vacantness of land, even if any individual would talk about land in fields or grounds, for immediateness.

For Internet:

In Internet, lot of resources and protocols are used to denote address, and we need to assign value, as per our permanent address, and temporary address by means of some parameters, so that, numbers like as IP address, DNS address, and lot of topics can provide us our address of physical reality, even allowing us to answer, where does any internet user resides with particular IP address and such address of computing.

Conclusion:

Addresses would be more rigid, accurate, and Bibliographical.

Advantages and Disadvantages:

1. Addresses would rely on choice of each individual.
2. Addresses would be hierarchial, depending upon family, as well as generations.
3. Trade based on Address Number would begin.

Mitigating Measures:

When we have both advantages and disadvantages created by same topics, we need some mitigating measures. Thus, verification of address and addressee would be necessary, as per nation, to protect freedom, and to avoid misuse of address.

Actknowledgements:

I had submitted application letters to Ward Number- 3 Office, Gauradaha Municipality, Department of Postal Address, Department of Cottage and Small Scale Industries, University Grants Comission, for works in addresses, as well as for registration of application letters. Thus I actknowledge my own application letters and administrations as well, irrespective of work, if they had done or not.